

OLFACTORY DYSFUNCTION AS AN EARLY MARKER FOR DIAGNOSIS OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE: A CASE CONTROLLED STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Introduction:

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by motor symptoms and a broad spectrum of earlier non-motor presentations. Among this range, olfactory dysfunction (OD) is recognized as one of the early non-motor symptoms. Detection of OD by standardized smell identification tests may aid with early diagnosis and clinical decision-making. In this study, we aim to determine the diagnostic utility of olfactory testing in distinguishing between PD patients and healthy controls.

Materials and Methods:

This was a case-control study conducted with 200 participants: 100 PD patients clinically diagnosed and 100 age and sex matching healthy controls. Olfactory function was evaluated using the University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT). On the Hoehn and Yahr scale, PD cases quantified to the severity of illness. Demographic data, clinical characteristics and UPSIT scores were tested and analyzed using SPSS Version 26.

Results:

The average UPSIT scores were noticeably lower in patients with PD (17.3 ± 5.4) relative to the controls (31.8 ± 3.9) ($p < 0.001$). Hyposmia and anosmia were significantly more common in participants with PD (68% and 20%, respectively). A UPSIT cut-off score of ≤ 25 provided a sensitivity of 88% and specificity of 85% in identifying PD. Olfaction was similarly associated with higher Hoehn & Yahr stage severity.

Conclusion:

Olfactory dysfunction is an early, prevalent, non-motor symptom in Parkinson's disease. UPSIT demonstrates excellent diagnostic accuracy for note taking with olfactory dysfunction being a simple non-invasive tool for supporting the early identification of PD.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, olfactory dysfunction, University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test, Hoehn and Yahr scale.

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive and neurodegenerative disorder that is typically identified by specific motor symptoms, including bradykinesia, rigidity, resting tremor and postural instability [1], mainly due to the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta. Apart from motor features, PD often presents with many non-motor symptoms (including sleep disorders, autonomic dysfunction, changes in mood, and sensory changes), which can appear beforehand[2]. Staging models of neurodegeneration indicate early involvement of extra-nigral areas including olfactory structures which is helpful in explaining non-motor symptoms, such as OD. The presence of Lewy bodies in the substantia nigra is a pathological hallmark of PD. Lewy pathology follows Braak staging, which describes the progression of the disease beginning in the olfactory bulb and dorsal motor nucleus of the vagus, which correlates with early olfactory dysfunction [3].

Olfactory dysfunction (OD) refers to decreased or lost ability to detect, discriminate or identify odors . This ranges from hyposmia (partial loss of smell) or anosmia (complete loss of smell), and includes a list of qualitative disorders (parosmia, phantosmia) [4,5]. OD can be caused by peripheral causes (nasal obstruction, sinonasal disease, viral injury to olfactory epithelium) or central causes (neurodegenerative disease). Clinically, psychophysical tests such as the University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT) or Sniffin' Sticks, is commonly used to quantify olfactory function in both research and clinical practice .

Parkinson's disease is amongst the world's fastest-growing neurological disorders, with an estimated prevalence of 6.1 million people identified by the Global Burden of Disease Study in 2016 [6]. The prevalence is observed to rise quickly with age, progressing from a prevalence of 41 per 100,000 in those age 40 - 49, to over 1000 per 100,000 in those age 70 - 79[7]. In India, community-based epidemiological studies indicate a considerable variability in the prevalence of Parkinson's disease. Crude prevalence estimates range from as low as 14.1 per 100,000 in rural Kashmir to high estimates of 45.8 per 100,000 from Kolkata, while the age-adjusted rate

estimated from Bangalore is 76 per 100,000 [8]. Most recently, a large meta-analysis estimated a pooled prevalence of 0.8 per 1,000 (~80 per 100,000) (95% CI: 0.4–1.3/1,000) [9].

Olfactory dysfunction is among the earliest and most reliable nonmotor symptoms of Parkinson's disease. Structural and neurochemical changes in olfactory pathways occurs during the early stage of disease process which makes smell impairment a reliable indicator of PD. Olfactory testing is recognized as a valuable tool for the early detection of PD and it is non-invasive, simple and highly sensitive.

The present study aims to assess olfactory dysfunction as an early diagnostic marker of Parkinson's Disease in a case-controlled design. The primary objective is to evaluate olfactory function (measured with a validated psychophysical test) in people with early/clinically diagnosed PD.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Population:

A total of 200 participants were included in the study, comprising 100 clinically diagnosed Parkinson's disease patients and 100 age and sex matched healthy controls. Participants were recruited from the Neurology outpatient department of a tertiary care hospital in South India.

Study Design:

This was a case-controlled observational study conducted over a period of 12 months, from September 2024 to September 2024.

Inclusion Criteria:

For Patients with Parkinson's Disease (PD Group):

1. A clinical diagnosis of Parkinson's disease.
2. Age 45-75 years.
3. Able and willing to give informed consent.

For Controls:

1. Age- and sex-matched healthy individuals with no history of neurological disease.
2. No prior history of olfactory dysfunction or chronic sinonasal disease.
3. Able and willing to give informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

1. History of chronic sinusitis, nasal polyposis, or other recent upper respiratory infection.
2. History of head injury within the last 6 months.
3. Cognitive impairment that would interfere with olfactory testing.
4. Chemical or toxin exposure known to impair smell function.
5. History of any neurodegenerative disorders unrelated to Parkinson's disease.

Assessment Tools:

- University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT) was used to determine the olfactory function. UPSIT is a standardized 40-item smell identification test that allows for quantitative assessment of olfactory performance [10].
- Disease severity in Parkinson's disease was evaluated using the Hoehn and Yahr staging system [11], which classifies patients into stages to evaluate functional impairment and the progression of motor symptoms.
- Demographic details, clinical characteristics, disease duration, motor and medications were recorded using a structured proforma.

Procedure:

Eligible participants first completed an extensive clinical evaluation that included a neurological exam for PD patients and screening for conditions that affects the olfactory function (e.g., Parkinson's disease, neurodegenerative disorders). After informed consent was obtained, demographic and clinical information was recorded.

All participants completed the olfactory testing in a quiet, well-ventilated room and under consistently applied standardized conditions. Participants were instructed to identify a series of odorants presented in a fixed sequence with scores recorded for the ability to identify smell. For the PD group, all olfactory testing was administered while in the "ON" medication state to minimize the impact of motor restrictions. Clinical staging of symptoms and severity of all applicable symptoms were documented for all PD cases.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analysed using the SPSS Software version 26 (IBM Corp., USA). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographics and clinical

characteristics. Differences between the cases and controls were analyzed using independent t-test for continuous variables and Chi-square test / Fisher’s test for categorical variables. The diagnostic characteristics of olfactory testing were determined using sensitivity, specificity, and ROC curve analysis. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant. Logistic regression was applied to identify the predictors of olfactory impairment in PD patients.

Figure 1: Hoehn and Yahr Scoring System

UPSIT Score	Outcome
6–18	Anosmia (complete loss of smell)
19–25	Severe microsmia
26–30 in women and 26–29 in men	Moderate microsmia
31–34 in women and 30–33 in men	Mild microsmia
>34 in women and 33 in men	Normosmia (normal smell appreciation)

Figure 2: University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT) Scores and Outcomes

OBSERVATIONS & RESULTS:

Variable	PD Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	61.4 ± 7.2	60.8 ± 6.9	0.52
Gender (Male/Female)	62 / 38	59 / 41	0.64
Residential Background (Urban/Rural)	48 / 52	51 / 49	0.68
Education Level (Primary/Secondary/Graduate)	30 / 45 / 25	28 / 47 / 25	0.88
Mean Disease Duration	4.8 ± 2.1	-	-

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Table 1 illustrates the demographic characteristics of the PD and control groups, where there were no statistically significant differences between groups regarding age ($p = 0.52$), gender ($p = 0.64$), Residential Background ($p = 0.68$), or educational level ($p = 0.88$). Therefore, patients were well matched and comparable for baseline characteristics.

Hoehn & Yahr Stage	Clinical Description	Number of Patients (n = 100)	Percentage (%)
Stage 1	Unilateral involvement only	18	18%
Stage 2	Bilateral involvement without postural instability	32	32%
Stage 3	Postural instability, physically independent	28	28%
Stage 4	Severe disability, still able to walk or stand unassisted	15	15%
Stage 5	Wheelchair-bound or bedridden unless assisted	7	7%

Table 2: Distribution of Hoehn & Yahr Staging Among Parkinson's Disease Patients

Table 2 demonstrates that the majority of patients with PD were distributed in Hoehn & Yahr Stages 2 (32%) and 3 (28%), defined as mild and moderate disease severity, respectively. Only 7% of patients were classified as Stage 5, thus indicating fewer patients with very advanced disability in the study population.

UPSIT Score Category	PD Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Mean UPSIT Score	17.3 ± 5.4	31.8 ± 3.9	<0.001
Normal Olfaction (%)	12%	82%	
Hyposmia (%)	68%	16%	
Anosmia (%)	20%	2%	

Table 3: UPSIT Scores Between PD Patients and Controls

Table 3 comparably describes a mean UPSIT score for PD patients of 17.3 ± 5.4, which was significantly lower than the average score in controls (31.8 ± 3.9), $p < 0.001$. The frequencies of hyposmia and anosmia were also significantly higher in PD patients, and this study highlights a strong association between olfactory dysfunction and Parkinson's Disease.

Severity Parameter	Mild (Stage I–II)	Moderate/Severe (Stage III–IV)	p-value
Mean UPSIT Score	20.4 ± 4.9	13.1 ± 3.8	<0.001
Hyposmia (%)	58%	76%	0.03
Anosmia (%)	8%	32%	<0.001

Table 4: Correlation of Olfactory Dysfunction with Disease Severity (PD Group Only)

Table 4 demonstrates moderate to severe PD patients (UPSIT score of 13.1 ± 3.8) had significantly lower UPSIT score compared to mild stage PD patients (UPSIT score of 20.4 ± 4.9), $p < 0.001$. Increased rates of hyposmia and anosmia in advanced stage patients further supports that olfactory dysfunction is strongly related to disease severity.

Parameter	Value
Cut-off UPSIT Score	≤ 25
Sensitivity (%)	88%
Specificity (%)	85%
Positive Predictive Value (%)	86%
Negative Predictive Value (%)	87%

Table 5: Diagnostic Accuracy of Olfactory Testing (UPSIT) for Identifying PD

Table 5 describes that a UPSIT cut-off score of ≤ 25 has high diagnostic accuracy for PD diagnosis with an 88% sensitivity and 85% specificity which confirms excellent discriminative ability, thus further supporting the use of the UPSIT as a valuable diagnostic tool for early Parkinson's Disease.

DISCUSSION:

The PD and control groups were matched well with no significant difference in age (61.4 ± 7.2 vs 60.8 ± 6.9 years, $p = 0.52$) or in gender distribution (62% vs 59% male, $p = 0.64$). Residential background and level of education were also equivalent ($p > 0.05$), suggesting demographic variables did not impact our outcomes. The mean duration of disease with PD was 4.8 ± 2.1 years, indicating that most participants in the study had early to mid-stage PD diagnosis. The similarity in demographic variables adds reliability to olfactory differences between groups. In the study conducted by Tohanean et al.[12], there was a greater proportion of women in the cohort with PD than men (62.5% vs 37.5%), with the majority being aged 50–59 and 60–69 years. Similar to our findings, they found the majority of individuals in the cohort were in Hoehn & Yahr Stage 2 (predominantly mild to moderate).

Most individuals diagnosed with Parkinson's disease in our study were in the mild to moderate range of Hoehn & Yahr staging, more prominently Stage 2 (32%), followed by Stage 3 (28%) and only 7% in Stage 5. Early disease (Stage 1) accounted for 18% of the cohort and Stage 4 was 15%. Overall, 60% of the participants was in Stages 2-3, indicating an ambulatory group suitable for measuring non-motor symptoms such as olfactory dysfunction. Müller et al [13] showed that people with Parkinson's disease had significantly longer rates of progression through Hoehn & Yahr stages compared with atypical parkinsonian disease, with none of the PD patients reaching Stage III within 1 year, but 72% of patients with APD reaches Stage III within an year.

Our findings confirmed a significantly higher burden of olfactory dysfunction in PD patients as compared to controls. Mean UPSIT scores of the PD group were significantly lower (17.3 ± 5.4 vs 31.8 ± 3.9 ; $p < 0.001$), with hyposmia (68% vs 16%) and anosmia (20% vs 2%) also significantly more common ($p < 0.001$). Only 12% of the PD group had normal olfactory function compared to 82% of the controls, confirming severe and significant olfactory dysfunction in Parkinson's Disease.

Similarly, Kwak et al.[14] reported that 70.5% of patients with PD had olfactory dysfunction, with 35.9% having hyposmia and 35.9% having anosmia.

Our study results found a definite relationship between worsening olfactory function and increasing disease severity. Patients classified as Hoehn & Yahr Stages III–IV had significantly lower UPSIT scores (13.1 ± 3.8) than patients evaluated in earlier stages of disease (20.4 ± 4.9 ; $p < 0.001$). Anosmia was significantly more common in the advanced disease state (32% vs 8%); hyposmia was more frequently observed and experienced an increase in proportion from 58% to 76% ($p = 0.03$). These findings indicate that the olfactory dysfunction worsens along with increased motor severity. Quagliato et al.[15] also noted significantly lower scores on the UPSIT in PD patients (mean 5.7) compared to controls (9), and showed a negative correlation with worsened olfactory function due to advancing Hoehn & Yahr condition stage.

The findings of this study demonstrated that olfactory testing can be performed with a high degree of diagnostic accuracy to determine the Parkinson's disease. A UPSIT cut-off score of ≤ 25 demonstrated high sensitivity (88%) and specificity (85%) along with a PPV of 86% and NPV of 87%. Landolfi et al [16]. also showed strong diagnostic capability with their 40-item UPSIT, with comparable diagnostic capability (sens. 82%, spec. 88.2%, cut-off ≤ 21), further establishing the consistency of smell identification testing in distinguishing between individuals with a PD diagnosis and those without a PD diagnosis.

CONCLUSION:

This study demonstrated that olfactory dysfunction is an early and significant non-motor symptom of Parkinson's disease, with scores on the UPSIT showing significantly impaired scores than healthy control participants. The olfactory impairment also correlated with increasing disease severity, underscoring its clinical relevance. Therefore, the study indicates that smell testing is a simple, non-invasive, and valuable tool to support early clinical diagnosis of Parkinson's disease.

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